

SPATIAL AWARENESS AND INFLUENCE FOR CO-CREATIVE AGENTS: INTRODUCING AUTOMATED CORPUS SPATIALIZATION IN SOMAX2

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a novel methodology for creating dynamic auditory landscapes in co-creative musical interaction through the Somax2 system, introducing a new approach to spatial awareness and agent interaction. By utilizing a custom Circular Auto Spat (CAS) module within an Ambisonics configuration, our system allows agents to perceive their spatial positions and influence each other's behavior based on localization. This spatial awareness fosters deeper, more interactive dynamics among agents. A key feature is enabling musicians to “play the space”, controlling both the agents and evolving auditory scene through spatial engagement and spatial influences. Musicians can shape soundscapes in real-time, manipulating relationships between sound sources based on their position and movement. The system employs Ambisonics as the diffusion decoding protocol for spatialization, ensuring an immersive and responsive auditory environment. This implementation bridges interactive music systems with auditory landscape design, offering a new tool for augmenting improvised soundscapes. By automating the spatialization of sound sources based on their audio features and roles in the interaction, our system facilitates the creation of immersive, responsive environments that enhance co-creative expression and improvisational interaction.

1. INTRODUCTION

Spatialization is a fundamental aspect of contemporary sound design and composition, shaping auditory perception by controlling the placement and movement of sound sources in a given environment. Various spatialization techniques [1] have been developed to accommodate different creative and technological needs, including amplitude or intensity panning, Ambisonics, Wave Field Synthesis (WFS), and binaural rendering [2]. The integration of real-time spatialization with feature-based analysis has led to novel approaches in interactive performance, adaptive music systems, and immersive installations [3,4]. In interactive systems, spatial attributes can be dynamically controlled based on pitch, loudness, spectral characteristics, or gestural input. One notable framework is Corpus-Based

Concatenative Synthesis (CBCS), implemented in tools such as MuBu and CataRT [5]. These tools allow real-time segmentation and spatialization of audio grains based on descriptors such as MFCCs and spectral centroid, facilitating dynamic spatial movement. From this paradigm, several human-machine music composition and improvisation applications have been developed, particularly within the REACH project at IRCAM, such as Omax [6], Djazz [7], Dicy2 [8], and Somax2 [9]. While these systems effectively analyze, model, and interact with musicians in real time, they lack spatial awareness. This limitation reduces their capacity to create immersive, spatially dynamic improvisation environments, potentially constraining their interactivity and co-creative potential.

We propose to address this limitation by introducing an automated spatialization system for corpus-based improvisation, integrating transient detection, spectral descriptors analysis, and Ambisonics encoding, focus, and decoding. This system, designed as an extension for Somax2 [9], enhances the spatial awareness of both human musicians and co-creative agents, allowing them to interact not only through musical content but also through spatial positioning. The spatialization approach follows two core interaction principles: (1) fully automated spatialization, where agents' positions are determined algorithmically based on spectral features, and (2) influencer-dependent spatialization, where certain agents exert control over others' spatial behavior, shaping the emergent auditory landscape. A key contribution of our system is the Circular Auto Spat (CAS) module, which converts analytical audio signal data into spatial information. CAS employs a dynamic model for generating circular spatial trajectories with variable parameters, enabling a more organic, evolving spatial movement. By coupling CAS with real-time corpus-based improvisation, we introduce a new layer of interaction, where spatial relationships between sound sources become a fundamental expressive parameter.

This paper is structured as follows: Section 2 provides a background on spatialization techniques, audio descriptors, and relevant works that employ real-time or dynamic spatialization. Section 3 details the implementation of our automatic spatialization system. Section 4 introduces the CAS module and explains its different algorithms. Section 5 discusses the integration of our system with Somax2. Finally, Section 6 concludes with reflections on the impact of spatial awareness in corpus-based improvisation and potential future directions.

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2. BACKGROUND

2.1 Spatialization Techniques and Tools

One of the most widely used spatialization frameworks is spat~ [10–12], developed at IRCAM, which offers real-time spatialization techniques such as vector-based amplitude or intensity panning (VBAP, VBIP) [13, 14], distance-based amplitude panning (DBAP) [15], layer-based amplitude panning (LBAP) [16] high-order Ambisonics (HOA) [17, 18], wave-field synthesis (WFS) [19], perceptual room acoustics simulation, impulse responses measurements, and directional effects through Ambisonics filter banks [20]. Focusing on HOA, the HOA Library [21] provides tools for high-order Ambisonics encoding, transformation, and decoding, supporting immersive multi-speaker configurations. The main characteristics of this library are its open source code in C++, with implementations in various environments, such as Max, Pure Data and Faust. Systems such as SPAT-SCENE [22], on the other hand, allow spatial trajectories defined in time to be composed through spatial scene descriptors, to facilitate the creation and manipulation of spatiotemporal data even through interactive input. Other trajectory editors are Holo-Edit [23], Zirkonium [24], Ambicontrol [25] or IEM Suite¹ employing breakpoint curves, sequences of time-tagged points in a 3D space, or freehand drawing.

2.2 Audio Descriptors and Feature Analysis

Audio descriptors, also known as audio features, provide numerical representations of sound characteristics and are widely used for analysis, synthesis, and interactive applications. These descriptors can be categorized into temporal, spectral, and harmonic features. Temporal descriptors include RMS energy, zero-crossing rate (ZCR), and transient detection, which measure signal amplitude, noisiness, and percussive elements, respectively. Spectral descriptors such as spectral centroid, spectral flux, spectral flatness, and Mel-Frequency Cepstral Coefficients (MFCCs) provide information about timbral properties and frequency distribution. Harmonic descriptors, including pitch estimation, chroma features, and inharmonicity, help analyze musical tonality and resonance characteristics [26].

In real-time audio analysis, several Max/MSP libraries provide tools for extracting these descriptors. MuBu [27] is a powerful framework for real-time feature extraction and corpus-based concatenative synthesis. FluCoMa [28] enables advanced machine-learning-driven audio descriptor analysis. Other tools such as Zsa.descriptors [29], ircamdescriptor~, bonk~, fiddle~ [30], sigmund~, and yin~ [31] provide efficient real-time analysis of pitch, amplitude, and spectral content.

2.3 Real-Time Spatialization in Music Composition

Several contemporary music compositions have explored spatialization as a structural and performative element. Pierre Boulez's *Répons* (1981–1984)² was a pioneering

work that integrated live instrumental processing with real-time spatialization across multiple speakers. The spatial placement of sound sources responded dynamically to spectral transformations, highlighting spatialization as an essential compositional parameter. Other influential works include Jonathan Harvey's *Mortuos Plango, Vivos Voco* (1980)³, which used computer-based spatial techniques to create an immersive sonic environment, and Karlheinz Stockhausen's *Gesang der Junglinge* (1955–1956)⁴, *Kontakte* (1958–1960)⁵ and *Oktophonie* (1990–1991)⁶, which employed non real-time and real-time electronic spatialization in different setups to create immersive musical scenarios. John Cowing's *Turenas* (1971–1972) [32] embodies both sound localization and Frequency Modulation (FM) synthesis to create illusory motion of sound in space, through amplitude and frequency control functions for distance and Doppler effect shifts. More recent examples, such as Natasha Barrett's *Little Animals* (2008) [33] or Nicola Giannini's *Le vent qui hurle* [34], leverage real-time spectral analysis and Ambisonics to create evolving spatial trajectories [35].

2.4 Proposed Workflow

While spatialization is well studied in composition, it remains underexplored in music improvisation, where both technique and awareness are often limited. Our approach addresses this gap by integrating real-time spatialization into improvisation systems. Using Somax2 [9], a co-creative improvisation tool, we move from fixed spatialization to an interactive process shaped by musicians and AI. Beyond technical contributions, we aim to rethink how space is perceived, felt, and played in improvisation, opening new possibilities for human-AI collaboration.

In many contemporary contexts, spatialization is either predetermined or governed by pseudo-random algorithms, rendering it secondary to performance. We challenge this by developing a system where spatialization emerges from the act of improvising. Somax2 is coupled with a Max/MSP external that analyzes performers' timbral features in real time, letting spatial movement be driven by sound itself. The system listens, analyzes, and translates sonic features into spatial gestures, creating a direct link between sound and space. Instead of relying exclusively on direct numerical mapping between signal parameters and spatial coordinates, our system incorporates audio descriptors whose behavior correlates with perceptual dimensions, offering a complementary logic for spatialization. Our logic follows metaphorical mappings: (i) sustained sounds *expand* spatially; (ii) percussive attacks *trigger sudden directional shifts*; and (iii) frequency distribution *aligns with perceived spatial height*—with higher pitches suggesting elevation and distance, and lower frequencies implying proximity and weight.

³ <https://brahms.ircam.fr/fr/work/mortuos-plango-vivos-voco>

⁴ <https://brahms.ircam.fr/fr/work/gesang-der-junglinge>

⁵ <https://brahms.ircam.fr/fr/work/kontakte-1>

⁶ <https://brahms.ircam.fr/fr/work/oktophonie>

¹ <https://plugins.iem.at>

² <https://brahms.ircam.fr/fr/work/repons-1>

These perceptual *metaphors* let spatialization arise organically from performance. While inspired by acousmatic traditions, which separate sound from source, our system introduces autonomy: sound determines its spatial trajectory. Space becomes an active agent in improvisation, shaped by the music itself. By making spatialization a responsive, integral element of improvisation, our system expands expressive possibilities, embedding spatial movement within the musical gesture and redefining real-time interaction with space.

3. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Our proposed real-time spatialization system is implemented in the Max/MSP environment using externals belonging to the MuBu⁷, Spat5⁸ and MaxSoundBox⁹ libraries. This enables a real-time spectral analysis of the timbre of one or more sound sources, which is subsequently encoded in an Ambisonics system [11, 36].

3.1 Audio Analysis

The processing flow, as detailed in Figure 1, starts with the Audio Analysis module (1), which employs Spectral Descriptors (2) (window size 2048, hop size 1024) to extract spectral parameters such as perceptual loudness, spectral centroid, spectral rolloff, perceptual spread and spectral variation [10, 26, 37]. In parallel, a Transient Detection module (2) dynamically adjusts a detection threshold to increase sensitivity to transients, using `gen~`¹⁰, `bonk~`¹¹ and `pipo~`¹² (fft size 1024, hop size 512).

3.2 Circular Auto Spat

The analytical data is transmitted to the Circular Auto Spat (CAS) module (3), which controls the spatialization of the sound source. Since this module plays a crucial role in the operation of our system, it will be further detailed in Section 4. In this context, the spectral descriptors determine the azimuth, elevation and distance (*aed*) parameters in real time, synchronizing the movement of the source with its timbral characteristics. The speed of rotation is calculated as a combination of spectral variation and the standard deviation of the perceptual spread, providing a dynamic mapping of the spatial behavior of the source according to the following heuristic rule: “*the louder and more unstable the sound, the greater its speed of movement in space*” [22, 38, 39].

3.3 Ambisonics Encoder and Focus

The analytical output of the system is processed by the Ambisonics Encoder (4) and Ambisonics Focus (5) modules, which take care of:

⁷ <https://forum.ircam.fr/projects/detail/mubu/>

⁸ <https://forum.ircam.fr/projects/detail/spat/>

⁹ <https://forum.ircam.fr/projects/detail/max-sound-box/>

¹⁰ https://docs.cycling74.com/userguide/gen/_gen_overview/

¹¹ <https://pd.iem.sh/objects/bonk~/>

¹² <https://ismm.ircam.fr/pipo/>

Figure 1. Flow diagram of our automated spatialization system.

- **Source positioning:** conversion of Cartesian x , y , z coordinates (previously calculated in the CAS module) to *aed* polar coordinates, using `spat5.hoa.encoder~` to generate dynamic trajectories in space.
- **Spatial focus:** application of the derived coordinates to the `spat5.hoa.focus~` object, which adjusts the spatial distribution of the source based on the weighted spectral spread by dynamically adjusting the selectivity parameter.

The system incorporates a control model based on the spectral composition of the source: higher harmonic coherence leads to a reduction in the amplitude of the occupied space, while more chaotic or diffuse signals expand more in the sound scene. The underlying metaphor is: “*the more sine wave-like the sound, the more the space contracts; conversely, a white noise tends to occupy more volume*”.

3.4 Decoding

To enable advanced simulations and spatialization tests, in parallel to an Ambisonics decoder (6), a binaural decoding mode is implemented through `spat5.binaural~`, which operates on five sources, each controlled by *aed* coordinates derived from the Ambisonics encoder. The number of sources is arbitrary and may be increased if needed, depending on the complexity of the spatial scene. Binaural performance is further enhanced by including an adaptive reverb, which more realistically simulates the depth and distance of the sound sources from the listener.

4. CIRCULAR AUTO SPAT (CAS)

4.1 A Module for Dynamic Spatial Trajectory Generation

The Circular Auto Spat (CAS) module represents an application for converting analytical audio signal data into spatial information, based on a dynamic model to generate circular trajectories with variable parameters of speed, direction, and radius. The adopted approach relies on the temporal interpolation of spectral descriptors, ensuring a continuous modulation of spatial variables based on the timbral characteristics of the input signal. The primary objective of the CAS module is the creation of trajectories ranging from simple to complex, directly influenced by real-time timbral analysis. The methodology used is based on the use of auditory metaphors to translate acoustic parameters into spatial dynamics. In this section, we detail the algorithms that comprise CAS and operate independently and in parallel with each other.

4.2 Source Speed

The speed at which the sound source rotates is defined by the metaphor: *“the more transients a sound has, the faster it moves.”* This speed is calculated as the product of Spectral Variation and the number of detected transients within an 8-second window. Transient detection is performed using a bang counter linked to a calibrated bonk~ object, with a pipo~ used as an onset detector. The transient analysis process adapts based on the signal’s timbral characteristics: for percussive sounds, pipo~ is used to identify transients, while for granular sounds, bonk~ is preferred. The result of this analysis is then scaled to a value between 0 and 5. Additionally, the derivative of Perceptual Spread, scaled between 0 and 1, serves as a multiplicative factor to modulate the product of Spectral Variation and the transient analysis. This factor ensures that the perceived speed of the sound source aligns with its spectral characteristics. The final speed value determines the rotation speed along the circular trajectory, expressed in Hertz (Hz), as illustrated in Figure 2. To maintain auditory clarity and prevent phase-related issues, this parameter can be manually scaled, with a maximum allowable speed of 8 Hz to ensure the movement remains perceptible.

Figure 2. CAS algorithm for source speed.

4.3 Rotation Direction

The direction of the sound source’s rotation, whether clockwise or counterclockwise, is defined by the metaphor: *“a sound with strong spectral acceleration conveys a perception of increasing energy, whereas a stable signal tends to stop. Similarly, a strong transient can trigger a directional change.”* This behavior is determined by analyzing Perceptual Loudness (p_l). When p_l exceeds a predefined threshold, a non-zero signal is generated, enabling the source to move. If its second derivative satisfies $\frac{d^2 p_l}{dx^2} > 3$, the rotation direction is inverted (+1 or -1), with the initial direction randomly set to either 1 or -1. Additionally, an extra switch between 1 and -1 is activated by another bonk~ instance with a high threshold, generating the detected transient signal for directional variation. This process is illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3. CAS algorithm for rotation direction.

4.4 Trajectory Radius

The trajectory radius is defined by the metaphor: *“the lower the pitch of a sound, the more it tends to remain centered; conversely, a higher-pitched sound moves towards the boundaries of the sound sphere”.* The radius is calculated using a combination of Spectral Rolloff (R) and Spectral Centroid (C), both of which are first scaled to a range between 0 and 2000Hz. These scaled values are then normalized to fall within the range of 0.01 to 0.5 to ensure a controlled distribution along the spatial trajectory. Specifically, the normalized trajectory radius r is given by:

$$r = \left(\frac{C + R}{4000} \right) \times 0.49 + 0.01 \tag{1}$$

Figure 4. CAS algorithm for trajectory radius.

This ensures the radius r remains between 0.01 and 0.5. Cartesian coordinates (X, Y) are then modulated by two sine waves, which are phase-shifted by 90° to ensure smooth and balanced movement along the horizontal axis. The coordinates are given by $X(t) = r \cdot \sin(2\pi ft)$ and $Y(t) = r \cdot \cos(2\pi ft)$, where f represents the frequency of the sine waves, and t is the time variable. This configuration guarantees that the sound source moves along a circular trajectory, with its position dynamically adapting

based on the sound’s spectral properties, as illustrated in Figure 4.

4.5 Source Elevation

The elevation of the sound source is determined by mapping the Cartesian Y -axis value to the Z -axis, with the resulting value scaled between 0 and 2. This transformation effectively converts the front–back movement into a top–bottom dynamic, giving the impression of vertical movement in the sound field. Alternatively, the Spectral Centroid (C), scaled between 0 and 4000Hz, can be used to control the Z -axis position within a range of 0° to 90° . Specifically, the Z -axis value z can be computed as:

$$z = \frac{C}{4000} \times 90 \quad (2)$$

This equation ensures that the Z -axis movement is mapped within the desired 0° to 90° range, dynamically adjusting based on the spectral characteristics of the sound source, as illustrated in Figure 5.

Figure 5. CAS algorithm for source elevation.

5. SPATIAL INTERACTION IN SOMAX2

5.1 Somax2: a Co-Creative Improvisation System

Somax2 is a co-creative system for human-machine music improvisation, developed by the Music Representation team at IRCAM - STMS lab under the REACH project. It extends the core principles of its predecessor, Omax [6], by building on the stages of listening, learning, modeling, and generating, while introducing the concept of *influences* [9]. These influences, which are the primary means of communication between the software agents and the human performers, consist of information, such as onset, pitch, and chroma, related to musical events. The system listens to, learns from, and responds to influences in real-time, co-creating music in dynamic and adaptive ways. The exchange is directional, where the software agents - called *players* - continuously send and receive influences, shaping the flow of the performance and maintaining a high level of interaction between the software and the human performers. Somax2’s learning phase utilizes the notion of *corpus* as annotated music material. Each player is assigned a specific corpus, which is processed through segmentation and annotation with labels like onset, pitch, and chroma. This annotated corpus allows the system to generate music by selecting segments that best match the incoming influences, facilitating interaction between human performers and software players in the system through CBCS [5].

The system is genre-agnostic, capable of interacting with a wide range of musical styles. It fosters dialogue between musical agents, focusing on the act of creation rather than any particular musical style. Somax2 generates music by activating memory *peaks* in its corpus, based on the influences received. These peaks evolve over time, with the ability to adjust for positive or negative matches and adapt to the musical flow [9].

5.2 Spatial Influences

Our implementation consists of an automatic corpus spatializer for Somax2, introducing the notion of *spatial influence*, which is a novel feature¹³. To implement this, our system operates in two distinct modes: one where the human performer plays a leading role in shaping the spatial distribution of sounds, and another where spatialization emerges autonomously based on the sonic attributes of all sources. These modes allow different levels of control over spatialization, offering flexibility in performance contexts. The interaction flow in the case of an external performer (*influencer*) and a Somax2 player is detailed in Figure 6, where the switcher to change modes is also visible in light blue after the CAS module.

5.2.1 Influencer Leader Mode

In this mode, the human performer plays a guiding role, influencing both the material generated by Somax2 and its spatial placement. This allows the performer to actively “draw” space with sound, shaping the spatial environment through their gestures. The interaction between the performer and the system creates a highly responsive sonic space where every musical decision impacts spatial distribution in real time.

5.2.2 Emergent Spatialization Mode

In this mode, spatialization is evenly distributed among all sound sources, including Somax2 players. The system analyzes each sound and determines its spatial positioning based on its timbral attributes. This approach creates an emergent [40] spatial network, where no single entity dictates movement, and spatialization arises naturally from the interplay of sonic events.

Through these two modes, we introduce in Somax2 the concept of *spatial influence*, expanding the system’s capabilities and providing a more immersive, interactive experience for performers and listeners alike.

5.3 Implementation

In the default mode (*Influencer Leader*), the input signal is analyzed in real-time and spatialized based on its spectral characteristics. This process operates within a three-dimensional perceptual space, where each new corpus is placed at an azimuth of 180° relative to the influencer, and the same principle is applied for elevation. This method allows for the spatial organization of multiple sound sources, ensuring that they do not perceptually overlap, thereby maintaining clear sonic separation.

¹³ A video demo of our system can be found at the link: <https://youtu.be/KfLUgZCF9M>

Figure 6. Flow scheme of our whole spatialization system integrated with Somax2 (case with one Somax2 Player). This interaction is scalable to up to four Somax2 players and one human influencer.

Figure 7. Spatial distribution of four sources in *Influencer Leader* mode: the top left one leads the spatial influence while the other players are automatically distributed as described in Section 5.3.

When multiple corpora (up to 4 in addition to the influencer) are present, the system calculates an optimal spatial distribution based on the perceptual loudness of each source. This distribution is calculated according to the formula $\frac{aed(\text{influencer})}{n_sources}$, where $aed(\text{influencer})$ represents azimuth, elevation and distance of the influencer, and $n_sources$ refers to the total number of sound sources in the system. For example, if the influencer is positioned at 0° , the subsequent corpus will be placed at 90° , the next at 180° , and so on. This ensures that sound sources are spatially separated according to Somax2’s hierarchical model, promoting perceptual clarity (see Figure 7).

When the mode is set to *Emergent Spatialization*, the spatialization of each corpus is independent of the influencer. In this mode, each corpus can move freely within the spatial sphere, allowing for more dynamic and flexible spatialization. The system utilizes the timbral properties of each sound source to determine its position, independent of the influencer’s location, thus enabling autonomous trajectories and spatial behaviors.

Additional real-time control parameters include:

- **Spread to Sensitivity** (default = 0): When activated, this parameter modifies the spatial distribution based on the spectrum spread. It narrows the acoustic field, which enhances the localization of moving sound sources and ensures clearer spatial definition (see Figure 8).

Figure 8. Graphical representation of the *Spread to Sensitivity* parameter processed by the `spat5.hoa.focus~`.

- **Elevation Influencer** (default = 1): When enabled, the elevation of sound sources is influenced by the x and y coordinates of the tone analysis, before being translated into aed coordinates. When disabled, the elevation follows the translation of the spectral centroid within the 50 – 4000Hz band, mapped to an angular range between 0° and 90° .

These parameters are adjustable in real time, allowing dynamic control over the spatialization of each corpus. The system’s flexibility is enhanced by its integration with IR-

CAM's Spat5 suite, which provides robust support for encoding and decoding spatial audio in both 2D and 3D configurations. The default setup utilizes a 3D 4th-order Ambisonics configuration, with the ability to adapt to specific performance needs, including scalability for varying numbers of sound sources and outputs.

6. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we introduced a novel automated spatialization system designed for Somax2, which enhances the co-creative dynamics in corpus-based improvisation through spatial awareness. By implementing an innovative spatialization approach, we enable Somax2 agents to perceive and influence each other's behavior based on their positions in space. This spatial awareness allows for more immersive and interactive musical environments, where both human musicians and agents can shape the auditory landscape in real time through their movement and spatial engagement. The system's integration of Ambisonics as the decoding protocol for dynamic spatialization ensures a highly responsive and immersive auditory environment. Our system was publicly demonstrated at the 2025 Forum Workshop in Studio 2 at IRCAM, Paris. This event offered an initial opportunity for practitioners to engage directly with the system and explore its interactive capabilities in real-time. The informal feedback collected during the workshop indicated that the users found the system intuitive to use and engaged in performance contexts. However, while the workshop served as a preliminary user experience, it did not constitute a structured evaluation. As such, a key direction for future research involves the design and implementation of a formal user study to systematically assess the impact of the system on musical interaction, user experience, and creative outcomes. Such an evaluation will be crucial for establishing the practical relevance and scientific validity of the proposed approach, and to rigorously assess the system's usability and its contribution to co-creative musical practices.

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